

Pregnancy and neonatal safety outcomes of timing of initiation of daily oral tenofovir disoproxil fumarate and emtricitabine pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV prevention (CAP016): an open-label, randomised, non-inferiority trial.

Article summary:

Pregnant and lactating women are at heightened risk of acquiring HIV due to physiological changes such as hormonal fluctuations, alterations in the genital mucosa, and potential exposure to HIV-positive or unknown-status partners. In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) for pregnant and lactating women at substantial risk of HIV, based on safety data from studies involving HIV and hepatitis B treatments and post-hoc analyses from PrEP trials. Despite initial clinical trials excluding pregnant women, emerging evidence, particularly regarding tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) and emtricitabine, suggested PrEP might be safe during pregnancy.

The CAP016 study aimed to evaluate the safety of PrEP during pregnancy by assessing maternal and neonatal outcomes in women who initiated PrEP during the second trimester or after breastfeeding cessation. Specifically, the study compared two approaches to PrEP initiation: immediate initiation during pregnancy versus deferring initiation until after breastfeeding cessation. The goal was to determine whether immediate PrEP initiation was non-inferior to deferred initiation in terms of maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

The CAP016 study was a randomized, open-label, non-inferiority trial conducted at a single site in Durban, South Africa. Participants were HIV-negative pregnant women aged 18 or older, at 14-28 weeks of gestation, and without major obstetric complications or significant laboratory abnormalities. Women were randomly assigned to either the immediate PrEP group, which received monthly doses of TDF and emtricitabine, or the deferred PrEP group, which received standard HIV prevention services.

The study's primary outcomes were preterm birth (less than 37 weeks), very preterm birth (less than 34 weeks), low birthweight (less than 2500g), stillbirth, and small-for-gestational-age (SGA) infants. Secondary outcomes included maternal and neonatal adverse events, such as clinical and laboratory complications. A composite outcome combining preterm birth, low birthweight, stillbirth, and SGA was also analyzed. Statistical analysis focused on non-inferiority testing using predefined non-inferiority margins.

A sample size of 884 women was calculated to achieve 80% power to detect differences in the primary outcomes. Binomial regression was used for analysis, and sensitivity analyses were conducted to account for missing data. Non-inferiority was confirmed if the upper 90% confidence interval (CI) of the risk difference between groups was below the specified non-inferiority margin. Two interim reviews using O'Brien-Fleming stopping boundaries were conducted during the trial.

Recruitment was halted in December 2019 due to changes in South Africa's PrEP guidelines, with a final enrollment of 540 women, of whom 500 had complete pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. Adherence to PrEP was high, with 87% of women adhering at 4 weeks and 95% at

16 weeks. Nausea and vomiting were the most common reasons for missed doses, but no significant renal function abnormalities were noted.

The primary analysis found no statistically significant differences between the immediate and deferred PrEP groups for preterm birth or very preterm birth, confirming non-inferiority for these outcomes. However, the immediate PrEP group had higher rates of stillbirth, low birthweight, and very low birthweight. The upper limits of risk differences for these outcomes exceeded the predefined non-inferiority margins, suggesting a potential safety concern for certain adverse outcomes.

Serious adverse events occurred in 12.5% of women in the immediate PrEP group compared to 9.3% in the deferred group. Four women experienced HIV seroconversion, but all neonates tested negative for HIV. A post-hoc analysis of the composite adverse pregnancy outcome (preterm birth, low birthweight, stillbirth, and SGA) found no significant differences between the two groups, confirming non-inferiority. No evidence of renal impairment was found in the immediate PrEP group, consistent with other studies on tenofovir-based regimens.

Nausea and vomiting were more frequent in the immediate PrEP group, particularly early in pregnancy, but these side effects were transient and did not significantly impact long-term adherence. There were no significant renal complications, supporting the safety of tenofovir-based PrEP during pregnancy, although continued monitoring is recommended for women with pre-existing renal conditions.

The CAP016 study provides important safety data on the use of PrEP during pregnancy. It found that immediate initiation of TDF/emtricitabine-based PrEP during pregnancy was non-inferior to deferred initiation in terms of preterm birth and small-for-gestational-age outcomes. Although higher rates of stillbirth, low birthweight, and very low birthweight were observed in the immediate PrEP group, these differences did not reach statistical significance when analyzed in the composite outcome.

The study also showed that PrEP use during pregnancy did not lead to significant renal complications, and adherence was high despite some transient side effects like nausea and vomiting. While the study's early suspension limited the ability to definitively assess rare outcomes like stillbirth and very preterm birth, the findings suggest that PrEP is a safe and viable option for pregnant women at high risk of HIV.

The CAP016 study highlights the need for further studies with larger sample sizes to confirm these findings, particularly regarding less common adverse pregnancy outcomes like stillbirth and very preterm birth. Ongoing monitoring of maternal and neonatal health is essential, especially in pregnant women with pre-existing health conditions.

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Journal:

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- The Lancet HIV is a journal dedicated to publishing original research, evidence-based reviews, and insightful articles that promote change or shed light on clinical practice

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- IF 12.8 2023